
**ABROGATION OF ARTICLE 370 AND ITS IMPACT ON INHABITANTS
OF KASHMIR**

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ABSTRACT

The northern region of India is home to Jammu & Kashmir. After India and Pakistan split up in 1947, the union territory of Jammu and Kashmir became a point of contention between them. UT of Ladakh borders Jammu and Kashmir to the east, the Indian states of Himachal Pradesh and Punjab to the south, Pakistan to the southwest, and Pakistan administered Kashmir (PAK) to the southwest. Jammu and Kashmir was once one of the biggest princely states of India. The population of J&K is 12,367,013 and the size is 101,387 square kilometres. India's battles with the Jammu and Kashmiri community and Pakistan's struggle for territorial control are central to the complex and protracted conflict over Kashmir. This long-lasting conflict includes political, social, economic, and cultural dimensions and affects millions of individuals in complicated ways. The area under union rule up until August 5, 2019, Jammu and Kashmir was a state of India. Jammu and Kashmir was designated as Indian union territory on August 5, 2019. The Supreme Court of India removed Article 370 and 35A in Jammu and Kashmir, granting the local population unique status. Curfews and strikes are implemented in the UT as a result of public outcry at the court's decision to revoke article 370 in J&K. In Jammu & Kashmir, all internet and communication services were unavailable. The prolonged closure of businesses and educational institutions has a negative influence on Jammu and Kashmir's economy. The Indian Constitution grants the state of Jammu and Kashmir temporary special autonomy under a clause known as Article 370. When Jammu and Kashmir was incorporated to the Constitution in 1949, it granted the region a unique status inside the Indian Union. The history of Article 370 began with the princely state of Jammu and Kashmir's 1947 accession to India. After Maharaja Hari Singh, the princely state of Jammu and Kashmir, signed the Instrument of Accession in October 1947, the region became a part of India. This enabled the Indian government to assist tribal groups backed by Pakistan in their efforts to stave off an invasion. The Instrument of Accession stated that the state will continue to be autonomous in all domains except foreign policy, finance, communications, and defence. Jammu and Kashmir was granted special safeguards under Article 370 of the 1949 amendment to the Indian Constitution. The state was allowed to enact its own constitution and was granted a tremendous measure of autonomy. When Jammu and Kashmir accepted its own constitution in 1957, it solidified its distinct character. The state possessed authority over several matters, exclusive rights over land and property, and its own flag. It might also indicate someone was a long-term inhabitant. Over the years, a number of presidential decrees have been issued to bring Jammu & Kashmir under

the jurisdiction of Indian law. However, the state continued to have its own identity and its people were governed by separate laws. Over time, despite its unique status, Article 370 underwent alterations and revisions. Jammu and Kashmir's autonomy was steadily diminished, and the state's relationship with the Indian Union becomes less clear-cut. The Indian government, led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, removed Jammu & Kashmir's special status and annulled Article 370 on August 5, 2019. Jammu & Kashmir is well-known for its travel spots. It has tourist attractions for both the summer and the winter.

KEY WORDS

Part XXI -foreign affairs- defence– communications-Article 370-Kashmir Despatch-Emergency Powers-legal and political process.

INTRODUCTION

Article 370 granted special autonomous status to Jammu & Kashmir, allowing it to have its own constitution and laws different from the rest of India. The historical origins of Article 370 date back to the time of India's independence and the unique conditions under which Jammu & Kashmir joined India. Over the years, Article 370 faced various amendments and judicial interpretations, reflecting changing political dynamics. The revocation of Article 370 in 2019 led to significant political and social changes in Jammu & Kashmir, including its reorganization into two Union Territories. The long-term effects of the revocation are still unfolding, with ongoing debates about the region's future political and economic landscape. Article 370 was crafted during the drafting of the Indian Constitution. It was designed to grant special autonomous status to Jammu and Kashmir. This provision was included to respect the unique circumstances under which the state acceded to India. The article allowed Jammu and Kashmir to have its own constitution and autonomy over internal matters, except defense, communications, and foreign affairs.

There has been an upsurge in protest and violence in Indian-administered Kashmir since July 2016. The trigger was the killing of Burhan Wani, the leader of the armed group **Hizbul Mujahedin** by the security forces in that month. There have been numerous clashes between the Indian and Pakistani military across the 'Line of Control', as the border between Indian-administered and Pakistan-administered Kashmir is called.

Incursions by armed groups into Indian-administered Kashmir from Pakistan-administered Kashmir have also continued. In February 2019, more than 40 Indian soldiers were killed in an attack in Pulwama.

On 5 August 2019, the Indian Government suddenly announced the [revocation of Article 370](#) of the Constitution, which grants the state of Jammu and Kashmir considerable political autonomy. The Government says this is a long-overdue measure that will help to stabilise the situation by integrating the state fully into India. But there are fears that this move will only add fuel to the flames.

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

Article 370 of the Indian Constitution was a temporary provision that granted special status to the state of Jammu and Kashmir (J&K). Its origins can be traced to the circumstances surrounding J&K's accession to India in 1947. At the time of India's independence, princely states were given the option to join either India or Pakistan. The ruler of J&K, Maharaja Hari Singh, initially sought to remain independent but was forced to accede to India following an invasion by Pakistani-backed tribal militias.

On October 26, 1947, Maharaja Hari Singh signed the Instrument of Accession, bringing J&K under India's dominion but only in matters of defense, foreign affairs, and communications. This led to the need for a constitutional framework that would define J&K's relationship with India, leading to the drafting of Article 370.

DRAFTING PROCESS

The drafting of Article 370 was a complex process shaped by negotiations between J&K's political leadership, particularly Sheikh Abdullah, and the Indian government, led by Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru and Home Minister Sardar Patel.

1. Sheikh Abdullah's Role: Appointed as the Prime Minister of J&K in 1948, Sheikh Abdullah played a key role in negotiating J&K's special status. He argued for maximum autonomy to protect the region's unique identity.
2. Gopaldaswami Ayyangar's Contribution: A close aide of Nehru and a former Dewan of J&K, Ayyangar was tasked with drafting Article 370. He advocated for its inclusion as a temporary provision, considering the unsettled political situation.
3. Constituent Assembly Debate: The provision was discussed extensively in the Indian Constituent Assembly. Some leaders, including Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, were skeptical about granting special status to J&K, but Nehru and Ayyangar emphasized its necessity due to the ongoing conflict in the region.

- Article 370 is a constitutional provision that gave Jammu and Kashmir its special status.
- The provision was incorporated in Part XXI of the Constitution: Temporary, Transitional and Special Provisions.
 - As evident from the title of the Part, it was supposed to be a temporary provision and its applicability was projected to last till the formulation and adoption of the State's constitution.

It restricted the Parliament's legislative powers with respect to the state of J&K.

Pandit Nehru, on the floor of Lok Sabha on 27th November 1963, said that Article 370 has been eroded and the process of gradual erosion is going on. A year later, the then Home Minister Gulzari Lal Nanda, again on the floor of [Lok Sabha](#) on 4 December 1964, said, Article 370 is a tunnel to take the

Constitution of India to Jammu and Kashmir. He further said that in the end, only the shell will remain there and it will be bereft of its contents, and it will hardly make any difference whether it is kept or not.

These two statements by two tall leaders of the country speak volumes about the dilution of Article 370 of the [Constitution of India](#) just merely after one decade of its enactment. The process had right away started in the year 1950, with the issuance of the Constitutional Application Order 1950, and thereafter, a number of parlances took place between the Centre and the State leadership, which evolved into an agreement known as the Delhi Agreement of 1952, wherein a number of subjects apart from those in the Instrument of Accession were agreed to be made applicable to the State of J&K. Some of them are as under:

- Appointment of the head of State.
- Persons having domicile in the State of J&K shall be Citizens of India.
- Fundamental Rights
- Jurisdiction of Supreme Court
- National Flag
- Financial Integration
- Emergency Powers

IMPLICATIONS OF REVOKING ARTICLE 370

Article 370 was added to India's Constitution in 1949. It allows Jammu and Kashmir to have its own constitution, a separate flag and independence over all matters except foreign affairs, defence and communications. This autonomy has been greatly eroded in practice over recent decades.

During recent national elections, which it won decisively, the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), led by prime minister Narendra Modi, [promised to revoke Article 370](#). Except for one clause to which the Government does not object, this happened by presidential order on 5 August.

A Bill has also been rapidly approved by both Houses of Parliament splitting the state of Jammu and Kashmir into [two federal \(also known as Union\) territories](#). One will be called Jammu and Kashmir, which will have a state legislature. The other is Ladakh, which will be ruled directly from New Delhi.

The revocation of Article 370 extends to a key provision added under it, known as Article 35A. This gives [special privileges](#) to permanent residents, including state government jobs and the exclusive right to own property in Jammu and Kashmir. It is intended to protect the state's distinct demographic character as the only Muslim-majority state in India. Others, including the BJP, view it as discriminatory against non-Muslims and harming development. It was introduced in its current form in 1954 but a similar law was in place prior to Indian independence in 1947.

Thousands of additional soldiers were sent to Jammu and Kashmir prior to the 5 August announcement. A curfew is still in force. At least two senior Kashmir opposition politicians and former

Chief Ministers, Omar Abdullah and Mehbooba Mufti, have been detained and there is a communication 'lockdown'. It is hard to find out what is happening on the ground.

IS REVOCATION LEGAL UNDER INDIAN LAW?

Many acknowledge that Jammu and Kashmir's political autonomy has been greatly eroded in practice since Article 370 was introduced. But is the act of revocation legal under Indian law? There are many differing views.

Constitutional expert Subhash Kashyap, has said [the order was "constitutionally sound"](#) and that "no legal and constitutional fault can be found in it."

But some lawyers assert that constitutional change of this kind [requires a two-thirds majority](#) in both Houses of the Union Parliament. Others suggest that it requires the approval of a body – the Jammu and Kashmir Constituent Assembly – which no longer exists, having been abolished in 1957 after the state constitution was agreed.

In addition, the Supreme Court has previously declared that, contrary to those who believe it was only supposed to be a temporary measure, [Article 370 has become a permanent provision](#) of the Indian Constitution. This has led some to question whether it can ever be legitimately revoked.

The Supreme Court will very likely be asked to rule on the constitutionality of the BJP-led government's latest actions. But this could take some time. The Court is already considering [a constitutional challenge to Article 35A](#).

Many critics of revocation regard it as [breaching the contractual basis](#) upon which the Maharaja of Kashmir decided to join India in 1947. Some lawyers think that this means there could be an international law dimension too.

PRESIDENTIAL ORDERS

Under Article 370 of the Constitution of India, the [President](#) had the power of issuing orders for the application of provisions of the Constitution of India with modifications, exceptions and amendments in the provisions. And this power has been upheld in several cases by the Supreme Court, e.g., in P. L. Lakhanpal vs the State of J&K.

As already said, for the application of other provisions of the Constitution of India to the State of J&K, the only mode available was the Constitutional Application Order. And the same was to be done with the consultation and concurrence of the State Government. The Presidential Orders, broadly speaking, deal with the following subject matters:

- Enhancing the jurisdiction of the Parliament to enact laws in the State of J&K out of the [Union List](#).
- Laws relating to an increase or decrease in the area of the State.
- Making provisions for the return of the permanent residents of the State who migrated to the territories included in Pakistan under permit for settlement.

- Providing for constitutional protection to the laws relating to permanent residents of the state, their special rights and privileges, employment under Government, acquisition of immovable property, settlement in the State, scholarship.
- Earmarking the number of seats in the House of the people, excluding the area under the occupation of Pakistan.
- Provision for delimitation of Parliament Constituencies.
- Transfer of judges from the High Court of J&K or to the said Court.
- Exclusion of the State List.
- Provision as regards the decision affecting the disposition of the State of J&K.
- Acquisition and requisition of immovable property on behalf of and at the expense of the Union.
- Provision relating to the use of the official language of the Union and in the proceedings before the [Supreme Court](#).
- Provisions for the proclamation of emergency.
- Provisions for non-application of the amendments carried out by the Parliament of India in the Constitution of India.
- Provision for [Governor](#) and the Election Commission.

In the year 1954, the Constitutional Application Order 1950 was renamed as the Constitutional Application Order 1954 and its issuance was the first infringement on the constitutional autonomy of the State of J&K. It culminated with the issuance of the Constitution (Application to J&K) Order, 2019. Article 370 itself was used to make it weak after remaining on the Constitution book for 70 years.

PROVISIONS OF ARTICLE 370

- J&K had its own Constitution and autonomy in all matters except defense, foreign affairs, finance, and communications.
- Indian laws would not apply automatically to J&K and required the state government's concurrence.
- Article 370 could only be modified with the recommendation of J&K's Constituent Assembly, making it difficult to alter.
- The Parliament needs the approval of the Government of Jammu and Kashmir in order to apply laws in Jammu and Kashmir. There are some exceptions such as Defence, finance, communication and foreign affairs.
- According to Article 370 no person from outside Jammu and Kashmir can purchase a property in Jammu and Kashmir. The central Government even has no power to proclaim a financial emergency in Jammu and Kashmir.
- Jammu and Kashmir are bound as a state under Indian Union by Article 370(1)(c). Article 1 exercises with the help of Article 370. If Article 370 is repealed, then Jammu and Kashmir will be termed an independent state until and unless new laws are made.

ROLE IN INDIAN INDEPENDENCE

The inclusion of Article 370 was influenced by the political landscape during India's independence. The princely state of Jammu and Kashmir had the option to join either India or Pakistan. The Maharaja chose to accede to India under certain conditions, leading to the incorporation of Article 370. This article was seen as a way to honor the terms of the accession.

INITIAL IMPLEMENTATION

Initially, Article 370 was implemented to provide a temporary framework for Jammu and Kashmir's integration into India. Over time, it became a point of contention and debate. The special status granted by Article 370 meant that Indian laws did not automatically apply to Jammu and Kashmir. Instead, the state's legislature had to approve them. This unique arrangement was meant to ensure the state's autonomy while being part of India.

The historical context of Article 370 highlights its significance in the political and social fabric of Jammu and Kashmir. Understanding its origins helps in comprehending the complexities involved in its implementation and subsequent debates.

FACTS ON ARTICLE 370

Article 370 – Temporary provisions with respect to the State of Jammu and Kashmir

(1) Notwithstanding anything in this Constitution,

- (a) The provisions of Article 238 shall not apply in relation to the State of Jammu and Kashmir;
(b) The power of Parliament to make laws for the said State shall be limited to

1. Those matters in the Union List and the Concurrent List which, in consultation with the Government of the State, are declared by the President to correspond to matters specified in the Instrument of Accession governing the accession of the State to the Dominion of India as the matters with respect to which the Dominion Legislature may make laws for that State; and
2. Such other matters in the said Lists as, with the concurrence of the Government of the State, the President may by order specify
Explanation For the purposes of this article, the Government of the State means the person for the time being recognized by the President as the Maharaja of Jammu and Kashmir acting on the advice of the Council of Ministers for the time being in office under the Maharajas Proclamation dated the fifth day of March 1948 ;

(c) The provisions of Article 1 and of this article shall apply in relation to that State;

(d) such of the other provisions of this Constitution shall apply in relation to that State subject to such exceptions and modifications as the President may by order specify: Provided that no such order which

relates to the matters specified in the Instrument of Accession of the State referred to in paragraph 1 of sub clause (b) shall be issued except in consultation with the Government of the State: Provided further that no such order which relates to matters other than those referred to in the last preceding proviso shall be issued except with the concurrence of that Government.

(2) If the concurrence of the Government of the State referred to in paragraph 2 of sub clause (b) of clause (1) or in the second proviso to sub clause (d) of that clause be given before the Constituent Assembly for the purpose of framing the Constitution of the State is convened, it shall be placed before such Assembly for such decision as it may take thereon.

(3) Notwithstanding anything in the foregoing provisions of this article, the President may, by public notification, declare that this article shall cease to be operative or shall be operative only with such exceptions and modifications and from such date as he may specify: Provided that the recommendation of the Constituent Assembly of the State referred to in clause (2) shall be necessary before the President issues such a notification.

APPLICATION OF 370

- However, the State's constituent assembly dissolved itself on 25 January 1957 without recommending either abrogation or amendment of Article 370, leaving the status of the provision on a cliffhanger.
- The provision was later held to have acquired permanent status by way of rulings of the Supreme Court of India and the High Court of Jammu and Kashmir.
- This implied that to apply a central law to the state on subjects included in the Instrument of Accession, mere "consultation" with the state government is required.
- However, to apply a central legislation to matters other than defense, foreign affairs and communications," concurrence" of the state government was mandatory.

JAMMU AND KASHMIR CONSTITUTION

- Article 3-> Relationship of the State with the Union of India:- The State of Jammu and Kashmir is and shall be an integral part of the Union of India.
- In the Preamble to the Constitution, not only is there no claim to sovereignty, but there is a categorical acknowledgement about the object of the J&K Constitution being "to further define the existing relationship of the state with the Union of India as its integral part thereof."

Constitution (Application to Jammu and Kashmir) Order, 2019

1. (1) This Order may be called the Constitution (Application to Jammu and Kashmir) Order, 2019.

(2) It shall come into force at once, and shall thereupon supersede the Constitution

(Application to Jammu and Kashmir) Order, 1954 as amended from time to time.

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2. All the provisions of the Constitution, as amended from time to time, shall apply in relation to the State of Jammu and Kashmir and the exceptions and modifications subject to which they shall so apply shall be as follows:-

To article 367, there shall be added the following clause, namely: -

“(4) For the purposes of this Constitution as it applies in relation to the State of Jammu and Kashmir-

(a) References to this Constitution or to the provisions thereof shall be construed as references to the Constitution or the provisions thereof as applied in relation to the said State;

(b) references to the person for the time being recognized by the President on the recommendation of the Legislative Assembly of the State as the Sadar-i-Riyasat of Jammu and Kashmir, acting on the advice of the Council of Ministers of the State for the time being in office, shall be construed as references to the Governor of Jammu and Kashmir;

(c) references to the Government of the said State shall be construed as including references to the Governor of Jammu and Kashmir acting on the advice of his Council of Ministers; and

(d) in the proviso to clause (3) of Article 370 of this Constitution, the expression “Constituent Assembly of the State referred to in clause (2)” shall read “Legislative Assembly of the State”.

TEMPORARY, TRANSITIONAL, AND SPECIAL PROVISIONS

Article 370 of the Indian Constitution was designed to offer special status to Jammu and Kashmir. This article allowed the state to have its own constitution and autonomy over internal matters, except defense, communications, and foreign affairs. This special status was meant to be temporary, but it lasted for decades.

AMENDMENT PROCEDURES

Amending Article 370 required the approval of the Jammu and Kashmir Constituent Assembly. Once this assembly dissolved in 1957, any changes to the article became nearly impossible. This unique amendment procedure made Article 370 different from other parts of the Indian Constitution.

JUDICIAL INTERPRETATIONS

Over the years, the Supreme Court of India has interpreted Article 370 in various ways. Some rulings reinforced the article’s temporary nature, while others emphasized its permanence. These judicial interpretations have played a crucial role in shaping the legal landscape of Jammu and Kashmir.

The provisions of the Constitution of India with modifications, exceptions, and amendments in the provisions have always been a point of contention and debate.

POLITICAL AND SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS IMPACT ON JAMMU & KASHMIR’S AUTONOMY

Article 370 granted special autonomy to Jammu & Kashmir, allowing it to have its own constitution and decision-making powers. This autonomy was a significant aspect of the state's identity. The removal of Article 370 in 2019 changed this dynamic, integrating Jammu & Kashmir more directly into India's legal and political framework. This shift has led to debates about the balance between national unity and regional autonomy.

PUBLIC OPINION AND POLITICAL MOVEMENTS

Public opinion on Article 370 has been deeply divided. Some viewed it as essential for protecting the unique identity of Jammu & Kashmir, while others saw it as an obstacle to integration with the rest of India. The revocation sparked various political movements, both in support of and against the decision. These movements have highlighted the complex nature of regional and national politics in India.

ROLE OF REGIONAL AND NATIONAL PARTIES

Regional parties in Jammu & Kashmir have historically supported Article 370, viewing it as a safeguard for the state's special status. National parties, on the other hand, have had mixed views, with some advocating for its removal to promote national unity. The differing stances of these parties have played a crucial role in shaping the political landscape of the region. The debate over Article 370 has also had a ripple effect on the geo-political relations in the subcontinent.

CONCLUSION

Article 370 has played a significant role in shaping the history and politics of Jammu & Kashmir. It granted the region a special status, allowing it to have its own constitution and autonomy in many areas. Over the years, this provision has been a subject of much debate and controversy. The recent changes to Article 370 have sparked discussions about the future of Jammu & Kashmir and its relationship with the rest of India. Understanding the historical context and impact of Article 370 is crucial for comprehending the complexities of this region. As we move forward, it is important to consider the perspectives of all stakeholders to ensure a peaceful and prosperous future for Jammu & Kashmir.

On 11 December 2023, a Constitution Bench of the Supreme Court unanimously upheld the power of the President of India to abrogate Article 370 of the Indian Constitution. This abrogation in August 2019 led to the bifurcation of the erstwhile state of Jammu & Kashmir into two Union Territories of J&K and Leh and also denuded the state of its special privileges. The top court said that Article 370 was only a temporary provision to facilitate the accession of the erstwhile princely state to the Union of India during a time fraught with internal strife and external aggression. Jammu and Kashmir's unique status was intended to expire, but only with the support of its citizens. Their lives and feelings were directly impacted by the Center's sudden disenfranchisement. The relocation will therefore undoubtedly have a big effect on Jammu and Kashmir's politics, culture, and demographics. The Jammu and Kashmir people should be contacted by the government to assure them of improved governance and security.

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